

1. Review title

The communication of uncertainty in medical interactions and its effects on patients and/or their caregivers: a systematic scoping review

2. Introduction

Healthcare providers have moral and legal obligations to inform patients about the uncertainties relating to their condition, care and treatment. Previous research suggests that the way uncertainty is communicated may be associated with different patient outcomes (Dahm et al., 2023; Medendorp et al., 2021; Simpkin & Armstrong, 2019). Research regarding healthcare providers' communication of uncertainty is scarce and scattered across medical contexts and scientific disciplines (Cox et al., 2021; Kalke et al., 2021). Insights are needed into the different ways in which uncertainty is currently communicated, and the effects on patients. These insights can empower providers to feel more prepared for such discussions. In turn, this can help to reduce the burden of uncertainty on patients through optimal information and support, enabling them to participate in decision-making for their health. This systematic scoping review is unique in its comprehensive approach to uncertainty in healthcare interactions, extending beyond one issue of uncertainty or medical context. It systematically aggregates research on uncertainty communication in health care, resulting in a comprehensive overview of both approaches to the communication of uncertainty and on its effects.

3. Objectives

Review question

In what ways is uncertainty communicated in healthcare interactions and what are the effects of various approaches to uncertainty communication on patients and their caregivers?

Aims

The aims of this systematic scoping review are two-fold, i.e., to provide a comprehensive overview of:

1. how communication of uncertainty takes places in healthcare provider-patient interactions; and
2. the effects of various approaches to uncertainty communication on patients and their caregivers

Methods

5. Eligibility criteria

We include published empirical studies that measured or described the (hypothetical) interpersonal communication of uncertainty in interactions between healthcare providers and patients (and/or their caregivers). This will include studies that focus on the effects of such communication. Publications from all years will be selected.

This is translated into the following inclusion criteria:

1. **Published in English**
2. **Original, peer-reviewed, empirical article**
Also allowing secondary analysis of previous data.
3. **Conducted in a medical context**
Including any in- or out-patient medical encounters. This excludes interactions wherein communication is the intervention, such as psychological counseling.
4. **Involving healthcare providers and patients (and/or their informal caregivers)**
Including residents and physiotherapists, for instance

5. Investigating real-life or hypothetical interpersonal communication

This may include non-verbal, verbal and/or written communication. Methods used may include, for example, (audio- or video) recordings of healthcare interactions, vignettes that elicit the (reported) communication of healthcare providers, or vignettes that elicit the response of (analogues) patients on healthcare providers' communication in response to various approaches of uncertainty communication.

6. Investigating communication (see 4) of uncertainty

Articles are included that describe the observed communication of uncertainty, for instance by reporting on expressions of uncertainty, or reporting on communication on an inherently uncertain topic, like the communication of prognosis. Additionally, articles may report the effects of such communication. The research may focus on communication by either the healthcare professional, the patient (or caregivers), or both.

Types of studies to be excluded

The following criteria will be used to exclude studies:

1. That are non-empirical (e.g., reviews, editorials, comments, preprints and conference abstracts)
2. That are not-peer reviewed (e.g., doctoral theses)
3. That investigate the communication about uncertainty by healthcare providers outside of the medical context (e.g., complementary and alternative medicine)
4. With a focus on communication that is not interpersonal (e.g., mass communication, information leaflets, vignettes without a simulated clinician-patient dyad)
5. With a focus on self-reported communication, or its effects, obtained through interviews of questionnaires
6. With a focus on the concept of personal insecurity

6. Information sources

Three databases will be searched:

1. MEDLINE
2. EMBASE
3. PsycINFO

7. Search

The search strategy was developed in consultation with a librarian, an expert in systematic search techniques. A scoping search identified key references that had to be retrieved by the search strategy. The search was formulated in Medline (see supplemental Appendix A for the full search strategy) and later translated to two other databases (EMBASE and PsycINFO). Three key concepts and their variations were included, namely: 1) uncertainty, 2) communication, and 3) interpersonal communication. Table 1 provides an overview of all relevant search terms, excluding adjacency operators (see Appendix A). The most recent search was performed on December 5th 2024.

After running the search, the bibliometric software VOSviewer (van Eck & Waltman, 2010) was used to identify clusters of articles that would not inform our review question, in order to exclude irrelevant terms with a NOT-operator, e.g. climate change, mice, rats, and thus reduce the screening burden on the reviewers.

Table 1

Uncertainty	Communication	Interpersonal communication
Uncertain*	Discuss or discussed	Referral
Probabilit*	Manage?	Consultation

Ambigu*	Convey*	Interact*
Unsure	Communicat*	Consult or consultation? or counsel*
Doubt?	Express*	Participant?
Imprecis*	Consult*	Conversation* adj2 analy*
Unpredict*	Counsel*	Patient?
(unexplained or ambiguous) adj2 symptom?	Consult*	Caregiver?
Probabilistic	Presenting	Parent?
	Respons*	Family
	Disclos*	Client

* Signifies that the search term may be succeeded by any combination of letters

? Signifies that the search term may be succeeded by any one letter

8. Selection of sources of evidence

All articles will be evaluated for eligibility in two steps. First, by assessing title and abstract, and second, based on the full-text. Title and abstract screening will be performed independently by two reviewers (LB and WKS) using ASReview, an AI open-source tool that utilizes active learning and multiple machine learning models to facilitate the screening process (Boetje & van de Schoot, 2024). The SAFE-procedure as proposed by Boetje et al. (2024) will be followed to correctly determine when to stop screening and ensure reproducibility and transparency of the screening procedure whilst using ASReview. Disagreements will be resolved in consensus meetings. If necessary, a third reviewer (MH) will be consulted.

Full-text screening will be performed independently by two reviewers (LB and WKS), using the web-based collaboration software platform Covidence (Veritas Health Innovation, Melbourne, Australia). Again, disagreements will be resolved in consensus meetings. If necessary, a third reviewer (MH) will be consulted.

9. Data charting process

For each included paper, the data will be extracted by one reviewer and checked by a second reviewer. Inconsistencies will be discussed until consensus is reached. If necessary, a third reviewer (MH) will be consulted. The software system Covidence will be used for data extraction.

10. Data items

The following data will be extracted using a data-extraction table, which will be adjusted iteratively.

General info

- Author and year

Methodology

- Study design (e.g., qualitative, quantitative, mixed-method, observational, experimental)
- Country (of data collection, possibly include original language)
- Setting (e.g., clinical vs educational)
- Healthcare setting (medical discipline like oncology, pediatrics, genetic counseling)
- Conceptualization of uncertainty (e.g., diagnostic uncertainty, Han's definition, or not-given)
- Operationalization of communication of uncertainty
- If applicable, the operationalization of the effects of the approach of the communication of uncertainty
- Characteristics of healthcare providers (N, age, gender, medical profession, years of work experience, native speaker)
- Characteristics of patients and informal caregivers (N, age, gender, diagnosis, native speaker)

- The aspects of uncertainty communication that are described or manipulated (e.g., frequency of expressions of uncertainty, implicit or explicit, non-verbal markers, providing-space)
- Is the effect of the communication of uncertainty reported?
- If applicable, outcome measures for the effects of uncertainty communication (e.g., trust, anxiety, information comprehension)
- Reported results of the communication of uncertainty
- If applicable, reported results of the effects of the various approaches to the communication of uncertainty
- Critical appraisal score

11. Critical appraisal of individual sources of evidence

To be determined.

12. Synthesis of results

For the included studies with a qualitative design, two reviewers (LB and WKS) will rephrase and/or summarize the extracted data based on a thematic qualitative analysis. This will enable us to create an overview of various approaches to uncertainty communication by healthcare providers as well as their differential effects. First, initial themes and categories will be created by the two reviewers independently. Second, these draft themes and categories will be discussed between the two reviewers to identify new themes and refine existing, overlapping themes. Third, the preliminary findings will be discussed among the research team to resolve remaining disputes. This process will be repeated iteratively until the research group reaches a consensus. For the included studies with a quantitative design, results will be synthesized descriptively. Descriptive statistics will be used to summarize key study findings and will be presented both narratively and visually, using tables and charts. Since the scoping nature of this review, no meta-analysis will be performed.

Key papers to be included

- Bhise, V., Meyer, A. N., Menon, S., Singhal, G., Street, R. L., Giardina, T. D., & Singh, H. (2018). Patient perspectives on how physicians communicate diagnostic uncertainty: an experimental vignette study. *International Journal for Quality in Health Care*, 30(1), 2-8.
- Blanch, D. C., Hall, J. A., Roter, D. L., & Frankel, R. M. (2009). Is it good to express uncertainty to a patient? Correlates and consequences for medical students in a standardized patient visit. *Patient education and counseling*, 76(3), 300–306. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2009.06.002> PMID: 19604663
- Blanch-Hartigan, D., van Eeden, M., Verdam, M. G. E., Han, P. K. J., Smets, E. M. A., & Hillen, M. A. (2019). Effects of communication about uncertainty and oncologist gender on the physician-patient relationship. *Patient education and counseling*, 102(9), 1613–1620. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2019.05.002> PMID: 31101428
- Cousin, G., Schmid Mast, M., & Jaunin-Stalder, N. (2013). When physician-expressed uncertainty leads to patient dissatisfaction: a gender study. *Medical education*, 47(9), 923–931. <https://doi.org/10.1111/medu.12237>
- Doty, A. M., Rising, K. L., Hsiao, T., Amadio, G., Gentsch, A. T., Salcedo, V. J., McElwee, I., Cameron, K. A., Salzman, D. H., Papanagnou, D., & McCarthy, D. M. (2022). "Unfortunately, I don't have an answer for you": How resident physicians communicate diagnostic uncertainty to patients during emergency department discharge. *Patient education and counseling*, 105(7), 2053–2057. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2021.12.002>
- Engelhardt EG, Pieterse AH, Han PK, van Duijn-Bakker N, Cluitmans F, Maartense E, Bos MM, Weijl NI, Punt CJ, Quarles van Ufford-Mannesse P, Sleeboom H, Portielje JE, van der Hoeven KJ, Woei-A-Jin FJ, Kroep JR, de Haes HC, Smets EM, Stiggelbout AM. Disclosing the Uncertainty Associated with Prognostic Estimates in Breast Cancer. *Med Decis Making*. 2017 Apr;37(3):179-192. doi: 10.1177/0272989X16670639. Epub 2016 Sep 29. PMID: 27681991.
- Gordon, G. H., Joos, S. K., & Byrne, J. (2000). Physician expressions of uncertainty during patient encounters. *Patient education and counseling*, 40(1), 59–65. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0738-3991\(99\)00069-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0738-3991(99)00069-5) PMID: 10705065
- Johnson, C. G., Levenkron, J. C., Suchman, A. L., & Manchester, R. (1988). Does physician uncertainty affect patient satisfaction?. *Journal of general internal medicine*, 3(2), 144–149. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02596120> PMID: 3357071
- Khazen, M., Sullivan, E. E., Ramos, J., Mirica, M., Linzer, M., Schiff, G. D., & Olson, A. P. J. (2022). Anatomy of diagnosis in a clinical encounter: how clinicians discuss uncertainty with patients. *BMC primary care*, 23(1), 153. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12875-022-01767-y>
- Kirkeboen G. (2019). "The median isn't the message": How to communicate the uncertainties of survival prognoses to cancer patients in a realistic and hopeful way. *European journal of cancer care*, 28(4), e13056. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ecc.13056>
- Lian OS, Nettleton S, Wifstad Å, Dowrick C. Negotiating uncertainty in clinical encounters: A narrative exploration of naturally occurring primary care consultations. *Soc Sci Med*. 2021 Dec;291:114467. doi: 10.1016/j.socscimed.2021.114467. Epub 2021 Oct 9. PMID: 34653685.
- Medendorp, N. M., Hillen, M. A., Murugesu, L., Aalfs, C. M., Stiggelbout, A. M., & Smets, E. M. A. (2018). Uncertainty in consultations about genetic testing for cancer: an explorative observational study. *Patient education and counseling*, 101(12), 2083–2089. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2018.08.002> PMID: 30082116
- Menichetti J, Gerwing J, Borghi L, Gulbrandsen P, Vegni E. Saying "I Don't Know": A Video-Based Study on Physicians' Claims of No-Knowledge in Assisted Reproductive Technology Consultations. *Front Psychol*. 2021 Jan 12;11:611074. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2020.611074. PMID: 33510688; PMCID: PMC7835634.

- Myronenko, A., van der Velde, P., Derksen, S. M. J. C., & Peerdeman, K. J. (2024). How should uncertainty about upcoming painful procedures be communicated? An experimental study into highly uncertain pain predictions. *Patient education and counseling*, 118, 108008. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2023.108008>
- Ogden, J., Fuks, K., Gardner, M., Johnson, S., McLean, M., Martin, P., & Shah, R. (2002). Doctors expressions of uncertainty and patient confidence. *Patient education and counseling*, 48(2), 171–176. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0738-3991\(02\)00020-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0738-3991(02)00020-4) PMID: 12401420
- Prins, S., Linn, A. J., van Kaam, A. H. L. C., van de Loo, M., van Woensel, J. B. M., van Heerde, M., Dijk, P. H., Kneyber, M. C. J., de Hoog, M., Simons, S. H. P., Akkermans, A. A., Smets, E. M. A., Hillen, M. A., & de Vos, M. A. (2022). How Physicians Discuss Uncertainty With Parents in Intensive Care Units. *Pediatrics*, 149(6), e2021055980. <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2021-055980>
- Stortenbeker I, Houwen J, van Dulmen S, Olde Hartman T, Das E. Quantifying implicit uncertainty in primary care consultations: A systematic compariso of communication about medically explained versus unexplained symptoms. *Patient Educ Couns*. 2019 Dec;102(12):2349-2352. doi: 10.1016/j.pec.2019.07.005. Epub 2019 Jul 4. PMID: 31288956.
- van der Velden, N. C. A., Smets, E. M. A., van Vliet, L. M., Brom, L., van Laarhoven, H. W. M., & Henselmans, I. (2024). Effects of prognostic communication strategies on emotions, coping, and appreciation of consultations: An experimental study in advanced cancer. *Palliative & supportive care*, 1–13. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1478951524000403>
- van der Velden, N. C. A., van der Kleij, M. B. A., Lehmann, V., Smets, E. M. A., Stouthard, J. M. L., Henselmans, I., & Hillen, M. A. (2021). Communication about Prognosis during Patient-Initiated Second Opinion Consultations in Advanced Cancer Care: An Observational Qualitative Analysis. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 18(11), 5694. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18115694>
- van Someren JL, Lehmann V, Stouthard JM, Stiggelbout AM, Smets EMA, Hillen MA. Oncologists' Communication About Uncertain Information in Second Opinion Consultations: A Focused Qualitative Analysis. *Front Psychol*. 2021 May 31;12:635422. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2021.635422. PMID: 34135806; PMCID: PMC8201772.
- Visser, L. N. C., Pelt, S. A. R., Kunneman, M., Bouwman, F. H., Claus, J. J., Kalisvaart, K. J., Hempenius, L., de Beer, M. H., Roks, G., Boelaarts, L., Kleijer, M., van der Flier, W. M., Smets, E. M. A., & Hillen, M. A. (2020). Communicating uncertainties when disclosing diagnostic test results for (Alzheimer's) dementia in the memory clinic: The ABIDE project. *Health expectations : an international journal of public participation in health care and health policy*, 23(1), 52–62. <https://doi.org/10.1111/hex.12964>

References

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- Cox, C. L., Miller, B. M., Kuhn, I., & Fritz, Z. (2021). Diagnostic uncertainty in primary care: what is known about its communication, and what are the associated ethical issues? *Fam Pract*, 38(5), 654-668. <https://doi.org/10.1093/fampra/cmab023>
- Dahm, M. R., Cattanach, W., Williams, M., Basseal, J. M., Gleason, K., & Crock, C. (2023). Communication of Diagnostic Uncertainty in Primary Care and Its Impact on Patient Experience: an Integrative Systematic Review. *J Gen Intern Med*, 38(3), 738-754. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11606-022-07768-y>
- Kalke, K., Studd, H., & Scherr, C. L. (2021). The communication of uncertainty in health: A scoping review. *Patient Educ Couns*, 104(8), 1945-1961. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2021.01.034>
- Medendorp, N. M., Stiggelbout, A. M., Aalfs, C. M., Han, P. K. J., Smets, E. M. A., & Hillen, M. A. (2021). A scoping review of practice recommendations for clinicians' communication of uncertainty. *Health Expect*, 24(4), 1025-1043. <https://doi.org/10.1111/hex.13255>
- Simpkin, A. L., & Armstrong, K. A. (2019). Communicating Uncertainty: a Narrative Review and Framework for Future Research. *J Gen Intern Med*, 34(11), 2586-2591. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11606-019-04860-8>
- van Eck, N. J., & Waltman, L. (2010). Software survey: VOSviewer, a computer program for bibliometric mapping. *Scientometrics*, 84(2), 523-538. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-009-0146-3>

APPENDIX A FULL SEARCH STRATEGY MEDLINE

Ovid MEDLINE(R) ALL <1946 to December 04, 2024>

Search date: 5 December 2024

#	Searches
1	uncertainty/
2	(uncertain* or probabilit* or ambigu* or unsure or doubt? or imprecis* or unpredict*).mp.
3	((unexplained or ambiguous) adj2 symptom?).mp.
4	probabilistic.mp.
5	or/1-4 [uncertainty]
6	communication/
7	((discuss or discussed) adj5 (uncertain* or probabilit* or ambigu* or unsure or doubt? or imprecis* or unpredict*).mp.
8	(manage? adj (uncertain* or probabilit* or ambigu* or unsure or doubt? or imprecis* or unpredict*).mp.
9	(convey* adj (uncertain* or probabilit* or ambigu* or unsure or doubt? or imprecis* or unpredict*).mp.
10	((communicat* or express* or consult*) adj3 (uncertain* or probabilit* or ambigu* or unsure or doubt? or imprecis* or unpredict*).mp.
11	((counsel* or consult*) adj4 (uncertain* or probabilit* or ambigu* or unsure or doubt? or imprecis* or unpredict*).mp.
12	(presenting adj (uncertain* or probabilit* or ambigu* or unsure or doubt? or imprecis* or unpredict*).ab,ti.
13	((respon* or disclos*) adj2 (uncertain* or probabilit* or ambigu* or unsure or doubt? or imprecis* or unpredict*).mp.
14	dialogue.ab.
15	or/6-14 [communication]
16	referral.mp. and consultation/ [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]
17	interact*.mp.
18	(consult or consultation? or counsel*).ab,kf,ti.
19	((uncertain* or imprecision or probability) adj5 (communicat* or discus* or convey* or express* or consult* or present* or respon* or disclos* or talk*) adj5 (counselee? or patient? or caregiver? or parent? or family or client?)).ab.
20	((uncertain* or imprecision or probability) adj5 (communicat* or discus* or convey* or express* or consult* or present* or respon* or disclos* or talk*)) and participant?).ab.
21	(conversation* adj2 analy*).mp.
22	or/16-21 [interactive communication]
23	and/5,15,22

- 24** exp animals/ not humans/
25 (Animal? or Rat or Rats or Mice or mouse or dog? or ape? or Monkey? or cat? or horse? or insect? or bee or bees or frog? or rabbit? or parasite? or cow? or dolphin? or forecast* or Ecosystem or Climate change or climate science).ab,kf,hw,ti. [VOS NOTing out]
26 24 or 25
27 23 not 26